

CHILD PROTECTION POLICY AWARENESS AND SCHOOLS' RESPONSIVENESS: BASIS FOR AN INTERVENTION PLAN

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ABSTRACT

Child protection is essential for safeguarding children's well-being, preventing abuse, and ensuring a supportive environment for their development. This study aims to establish a nurturing school community where all individuals feel connected, safe, and supported. It investigates the respondents' characteristics, child protection policy awareness, and school responsiveness, testing significant relationships and differences among junior high school teachers in the Valencia City division. Employing a descriptive correlational research design, 400 teachers were surveyed using the universal sampling method. Data was collected through adapted, modified, and researcher-made questionnaires. Statistical tools, including means, frequencies, standard deviations, Pearson's correlation, and ANOVA, were utilized to explore the relationships between policy awareness, school responsiveness, and teacher characteristics. The study findings reveal that most respondents, primarily Teacher I, have 6-10 years of experience and have received training on child protection policy at the school level. This indicates a strong foundation for child protection in our schools. The policies have significantly contributed to safeguarding children's interests, with schools demonstrating high awareness and responsiveness in disciplinary actions. There is a relationship between child protection policy awareness and schools' responsiveness. However, significant differences in school responsiveness were observed based on teaching position, experience, and seminars and training attended on child protection policy. Therefore, it is concluded that most respondents who attended seminars and training on child protection belonged to various tribal groups. Despite holding entry-level positions, the respondents gained experience over 6-10 years and demonstrated a very high awareness of child protection policy and school responsiveness. It is recommended to bolster teacher morale, provide

training for school personnel, strengthen monitoring and evaluation mechanisms, and adopt the proposed intervention plan.

Keywords: *child protection policy, schools' responsiveness*

INTRODUCTION

The Department of Education (DepEd) recently highlighted the importance of adhering to the government's child protection policy, empowering educators and staff to take a leading role in ensuring the safety and well-being of learners. This emphasis was in response to alarming statistics revealed by Vice President and Education Secretary Sara Z. Duterte, which indicated a disturbing trend in reported cases of child abuse from 2019 to 2022. In November 2023 alone, more than 1,700 reports of child abuse both in schools and at home were received by the Department of Education, indicating a disturbing trend.

In addition, within the jurisdiction of Valencia City, there had been documented cases of bullying and child labor, totaling sixty-four (64) cases between 2019 and 2022. Within 2023 alone, Valencia reported thirty-six (36) cases of bullying and physical injury. These statistics underscore the urgent need for schools to effectively address and reduce instances of child abuse, ensuring the safety and protection of their students. While policies and protocols existed to safeguard children, the effectiveness of these measures heavily relied on the responsiveness of educational institutions in implementing them.

The study was anchored on Republic Act 7610, also known as the Child Protection Act, which provides for comprehensive protection against child abuse, violence, and discrimination. Section 1 of the act, known as the Special Protection of Children from Crime, Violence, and Discrimination Act, provides that the state may intervene when parents, guardians, or other caregivers fail to protect children from abuse and exploitation.

Moreover, the Department of Education's Child Protection Policy (CPP) is a crucial regulation designed to combat violence, prejudice, and child abuse within educational institutions. The CPP not only encourages the public to report bullying incidents to the Child Protection Committee (CPC) for appropriate action but also plays a significant role in reinforcing the safety of students, as RA 10627 further strengthens the Department of Education's current child protection regulation.

Several studies have delved into the execution of child protection policies and the levels of awareness among implementers and authorities. A study found out that that teacher had a good grasp of the Child Protection Policy program implemented by the Department of Education (Asio et al.,2020). However, the study also highlighted the potential for higher responsiveness to the program in schools. Bayucca (2020) conducted a study showing that while teachers are aware of the child protection policy, its implementation in schools is only moderate. Additionally, Segundo and Guia (2019) conclusively determined that implementing the child protection policy was moderate in public high schools. Despite

the implementation of child protection policies and related laws, the stark reality is that children continue to remain at risk (Sapul,2022). Further, Munger and Markstrom (2019) discovered that personnel in schools had insufficient awareness of residential violence, including child abuse. According to Nohilly (2019), regular training and seminars are essential to ensure teachers are equipped to protect children's rights.

Guaranteeing the safety and security of children in schools is a paramount concern for education. An essential aspect of this endeavor is understanding the extent to which schools have implemented and are responsive to child protection policies. However, the level of responsiveness may vary depending on the characteristics of the individuals involved in upholding these policies within the school system. In addition, Adewale and Potokri (2023) emphasized that child protection is a collective responsibility that needs continuous efforts for policy implementation and goal achievement. Educators play pivotal roles in upholding school rules and policies, especially those related to child protection (Hoffman, 2020). The success of each school in meeting each child's unique requirements is an essential factor that must be evaluated.

Addressing these concerns posed significant challenges for both victims and educational institutions. This research aimed to establish a foundation for implementing effective school interventions aligned with child protection principles (Brown, 2022). It provides education authorities and policymakers with valuable insights to enhance the effectiveness of child safeguarding measures. The findings will help refine policies and implement more responsive and equitable approaches to protecting the rights and well-being of all learners.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the level of child protection policy awareness and schools' responsiveness in the Division of Valencia City for the School Year 2023-2024. The results served as the basis for an intervention plan. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

- 1.How are the respondents characterized in terms of teaching position, teaching experience, seminars and training attended on child protection policy, tribal affiliation, and attitude towards child protection policy?
- 2.What is the level of child protection policy awareness in terms of the establishment of a child protection policy committee, capacity building of school personnel, procedures in handling and management of cases, investigation and reporting, referral and assessment?
- 3.What is the level of schools' responsiveness in terms of disciplinary actions, stakeholders' involvement, support services, and monitoring and evaluation?
- 4.Is there a significant relationship between the child protection policy awareness and school responsiveness?
- 5.Is there a significant difference in the schools' responsiveness to child protection policy when grouped according to the respondents' characteristics?
6. Based on the study's findings, what intervention plan on child protection policy

can be designed?

Hypothesis

Problems 1, 2, 3, and 6 were hypotheses – free. Based on Problems 4 and 5, the null hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance:

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between the child protection policy and school responsiveness.

Ho2: There is no significant difference in the schools' responsiveness on child protection policy when grouped according to respondents' characteristics?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This research employed a descriptive-correlational research method to gather data. The descriptive method was used to describe a particular characteristic of the junior high school teachers regarding teaching position, teaching experience, seminars/training on child protection policy, tribal affiliation, attitude towards child protection policy. Also, the level of child protection policy awareness and level of schools' responsiveness. The descriptive aspect described characteristics related to junior high school teachers and child protection policies. This method enabled the researcher to comprehensively overview teachers' awareness levels and attitudes regarding child protection policies.

Further, correlational methods were used to analyze the relationship between child protection policy awareness and school responsiveness. The study incorporated correlational methods to examine the relationship between child protection policies and school responsiveness. This approach helped determine if there was a significant relationship between teachers' awareness of child protection policies and a significant difference in the level of responsiveness exhibited by schools in implementing the policy.

Study Setting

This research was conducted within the Schools Division of Valencia City, located in the province of Bukidnon, Region X of the Philippines. This division is renowned for its commitment to inclusivity and excellence, encapsulated in its mantra, "No Valenciano is Left Behind." This ethos underscored the division's dedication to ensuring that every student, regardless of background or circumstance, receives a quality education and support to reach their full potential.

Additionally, the Division of Valencia City emphasized the resilience and well-being of its learners, as articulated in the "TEN BELLOWS" advocacy of the Schools Division Superintendent. These guiding principles prioritized the holistic development of students, recognizing the importance of nurturing their physical, emotional, and social well-being alongside academic achievement.

The findings of this research held significant potential to enhance school responsiveness within the Valencia City Division. By identifying strengths and areas for improvement in implementing child protection policies, the study informed targeted interventions and strategies to strengthen the division's capacity to safeguard the well-being of its students effectively. This research contributed to the MATATAG Agenda and the division's ongoing efforts to create safe, inclusive, and supportive learning environments where all students can thrive academically, socially, and emotionally.

Research Respondents

The study's participants were the four hundred (400) Junior High School teachers teaching at National High School within the Division of Valencia City for the School Year 2023-2024.

Sampling Technique

In this study, the researcher employed universal sampling as the researcher aimed to gather data from the entire population of interest, ensuring comprehensive coverage and a high degree of representation in the findings.

Research Instruments

The research questionnaire was divided into three parts to gather valuable insights into child protection policy awareness and schools' responsiveness in the Division of Valencia City.

The first part of the questionnaire dealt with the respondents' characteristics in terms of a teaching position, teaching experience, seminars, and training attended on child protection policy, tribal affiliations, and attitude towards child protection policy regarding the attitude towards the Child Protection Policy the researcher obtained approval from Dela Fuente (2021) to utilize her questionnaire, which had a reliability rating of Cronbach's alpha of 0.980.

The second part of the questionnaire was adapted and modified to assess child protection policy awareness patterned on the DepEd Order No. 40 s. 2012.

The third part of the questionnaire dealt with school responsiveness and was a researcher-made questionnaire.

Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

The child protection policy awareness questionnaire was adapted from DepEd Order No. 40 s. 2012 and modified tailored to the needs of the study, and the researchers created a questionnaire on schools' responsiveness that demonstrated excellent internal consistency, with a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.965, indicating the questionnaire had an internal consistency rating of Excellent. The questionnaires underwent thorough validity

and reliability testing last April 5 to 7, 2024, at Lumbo and Sugod Integrated Schools. They were first evaluated by three (3) experts in the field: one who was a master teacher and child protection coordinator, one who was a research specialist, and the other who was a head teacher. This expert review helped ensure that the questionnaires were well-designed and appropriate for the study's objectives.

The validation results indicated that the questionnaire statements were well-organized and addressed various aspects of the school's responsiveness to child protection policy. To improve its effectiveness, a pilot test with a small group consist of 30 respondents was recommended to ensure that participants understood the questions and found them relevant to their experiences and perspectives. This step helped identify and clarify any areas that may have needed adjustment. Further, the questionnaire demonstrated high validity, ensuring unbiased data for the investigation with an error margin of only 0-5%. It exhibited exceptional clarity, coherence, and relevance, with well-defined measurement scales and response formats. Ethical considerations were thoroughly addressed, ensuring participant confidentiality and informed consent and mitigating potential risks to participants' well-being.

Afterward, after their recommendations were considered, the research instrument was pilot tested on thirty (30) public secondary school teachers who were not part of the respondents in the Division of Valencia City. This was done to ensure coefficient reliability and that the questionnaire was simple, appropriately administered, and adequate for data collection. The responses were tallied and run by the researcher's statistician. Furthermore, the questionnaire on school responsiveness demonstrated excellent internal consistency. Disciplinary actions: 0.961; stakeholders' involvement: 0.982; support services: 0.960; and monitoring and evaluation: 0.978.

Categorization of Variables

PART I. Respondents Characteristics

Teaching Position

Master Teacher III	Teacher III
Master Teacher II	Teacher II
Master teacher I	Teacher I

Teaching Experience

21 years and above	6-10 years
16-20 years	0-5 years
11-15 years	

Seminars /Training Attended on Child Protection Policy

International/ National Level	Division Level
Regional Level	School Level
District Level	

Tribal Affiliations

Bukidnon	Matigsalug
Higaonon	Tigwahanon

Manobo
Talaandig

Umayamnon
Others (Boholano,Cebuano,Ilonggo)

System of Scoring

PART II. Attitude towards Child Protection Policy

Scale	Range	Description	Interpretation
4	3.26 – 4.00	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
3	2.51 – 3.25	Agree	Positive
2	1.76 – 2.50	Strongly Disagree	Negative
1	1.00 – 1.75	Disagree	Very Negative

PART III. Child Protection Policy Awareness and Schools Responsiveness

Scale	Range	Description	Interpretation
4	3.26–4.00	At All Times	Very High
3	2.51–3.25	Most of the Time	High
2	1.76–2.50	Sometimes	Low
1	1.00–1.75	Never	Very Low

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher underwent an ethics review and obtained clearance from the Dean of Graduate Studies at PHINMA Cagayan de Oro College. After approval was obtained, the researcher sought permission from the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Valencia City to ensure alignment with the division's policies and guidelines. The researcher submitted the necessary documents, including the research tool, permit to conduct the study, and consent form, to the Superintendent for review and approval.

Once approval was obtained, the researcher sought permission from the principal of each participating school in the Division of Valencia City to access the schools and secure cooperation. The researcher communicated the study's purpose, objectives, benefits, and ethical considerations to the school principal to facilitate data collection arrangements and ensure respectful and collaborative conduct. Data gathering involved administering questionnaires to junior high school teachers in the Valencia City Division. The researcher provided clear instructions on completing the questionnaires accurately and honestly.

Data analysis involved tallying responses to identify percentages in the survey and identifying areas or aspects related to child protection policy awareness and school responsiveness that may require immediate attention or further investigation. The researcher's commitment to prompt data analysis and identifying alarming percentages ensured that the study's findings could improve child protection policy measures and school responsiveness.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The fundamental characteristics of the data in a study were described using descriptive analysis. Simple descriptions of the sample and the measurements were provided. Frequency and percentage were used to distribute the respondents on teaching position, teaching experience, seminars and training attended on child protection policy and tribal affiliations. The weighted mean and standard deviation (SD) were used to calculate the average of attitude towards child protection policy, child protection policy awareness, and level of school responsiveness based on respondents' responses. When grouped according to respondents' characteristics, the one-way ANOVA was used to determine the significant differences in the school's responsiveness to child protection policy. Pearson's Correlation Coefficient (Pearson r) was used to assess the relationship between child protection policy awareness and school responsiveness.

Scope and Limitations

This study focused on determining the level of child protection policy awareness and schools' responsiveness during the School Year 2023-2024 in the Valencia City Division.

It is limited to child protection policy awareness, such as the establishment of a child protection policy committee, capacity building of school personnel, procedures in handling and management of cases, investigation and reporting, referral, and assessment. The research is also limited to schools' responsiveness, disciplinary actions, stakeholders' involvement, support services, and monitoring and evaluation. Moreover, this research journey aimed to propose an intervention plan to address the child protection policy proactively and effectively.

This research involved four hundred (400) Junior High School teachers teaching within the boundaries of the Division of Valencia City. To ensure the study's representation was as comprehensive as possible, it exclusively involved teachers from large schools to mega schools in different tribal affiliations, ensuring a broad and inclusive cross-section of the teaching position in the division.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question 1. How are the respondents characterized in terms of teaching position, teaching experience, seminars and training attended on child protection policy, tribal affiliation, and attitude towards child protection policy?

Table 1.1 Distribution of Respondents Characteristics

Characteristics	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Teaching Position	Master Teacher 3	0	0
	Master Teacher 2	0	0
	Master Teacher 1	14	3.50

	Teacher 3	76	19.00
	Teacher 2	44	11.00
	Teacher 1	266	66.50
	Total	400	100.00
Teaching Experience	21 and above	46	11.50
	16-20 years old	34	8.50
	11-15 years old	56	14.00
	6-10 years old	162	40.50
	0-5 years old	102	25.50
	Total	400	100.00
Trainings and Seminars Attended on Child Protection Policy	International/ National	4	0.90
	Regional	28	6.60
	Division	64	15.10
	District	50	11.80
	School	276	65.40
	Total	422	100.00
Tribal Affiliation	Bukidnon	102	25.50
	Higaunon	6	1.50
	Manubo	0	0
	Matigsalog	0	0
	Tigwahanon	0	0
	Talaandig	34	8.50
	Umayamnon	0	0
	Others (Ilonggo,Cebuano, Boholano)	250	62.50
None	8	2.00	
	Total	400	100.00

Table 1.1 presents the respondents characteristics in terms of their teaching position, teaching experience, trainings and seminars attended on child protection policy, and tribal affiliation

The findings reveal that most respondents hold the position of Teacher 1, indicating an entry-level position. Most of these teachers have 6 to 10 years of experience in the field. Additionally, many respondents belong to various tribal affiliations such as Cebuano, Boholano, and Ilonggo and have participated in child protection policy trainings and seminars at the school level.

This suggests that while teachers have moderate experience, they often need comprehensive training in child protection policy, especially at international and national levels. There is also a noticeable lack of representation from specific tribal affiliations. Despite these gaps, teachers generally strongly agree with the attitude towards the child protection policy, particularly regarding safeguarding the interests of children. However, the results also indicate that relatively few respondents are in Master Teacher 1 positions, and even fewer have attended child protection policy seminars and trainings at the international and national levels. This points to potential gaps in the field's leadership development and capacity building.

Jones and Harris (2020) explored how different teacher categories affect the efficacy of child protection policies in schools. According to their study, Teacher 1, who is frequently

freshly certified or inexperienced, has less trust in implementing child protection measures than more experienced classifications such as Teacher 3 or Master Teacher. The findings suggest that child safety training should be customized to different teacher classifications, with younger teachers receiving more extensive support and resources.

Moreover, a study by Papay and Kraft (2019) emphasized that continuous professional development and opportunities for advancement are critical for maintaining an engaged and effective teaching workforce. On the other hand, Guarino et al., (2020) explored teacher tenure patterns in urban school districts and found similar variations in experience levels among educators. The researchers propose mentorship programs in which seasoned teachers advise less experienced colleagues in child safeguarding techniques. A study by Rabina and Writes (2019) found that teachers with higher qualifications and experience better understand child protection policies.

The finding reveals that many educators may need more awareness, knowledge, and readiness to implement and comply with child protection policies and protocols within educational settings. This gap underscores the need for increased investment in and promotion of comprehensive training programs at the international or national level to ensure that all teachers are well-equipped to safeguard children effectively, following the standards mandated by the Department of Education, Save the Children in the Philippines, and UNICEF

Dela Fuente (2021) points out the importance of regular and diversified training sessions in ensuring the successful implementation of child protection measures. Teachers who attend more frequent trainings, especially at the national and regional levels, are better prepared to deal with child protection issues. Furthermore, the report emphasizes that these trainings protect learners' and educators' well-being by equipping them with the skills and knowledge needed to address child safety concerns.

Martinez and Lopez (2020) address the issue of fair access to child safety training for teachers with different tribal connections. Their findings suggest that educators from underrepresented tribes (such as Higaunon and Talaandig) may have less access to thorough training than those from more prevalent affiliations (such as Bukidnon).

Nguyen and Tran (2022) stressed the necessity of culturally sensitive training programs customized to teachers' different tribal affiliations. Their findings show that training that respects and integrates the distinct cultural settings of various tribal groups are more effective in preparing teachers to deal with child protection issues. Culturally specialized approaches considering traditional practices and social dynamics help teachers from tribes such as Bukidnon, Higaunon, and Talaandig.

Table 1.2 Distribution of Respondents Attitude towards Child Protection Policy

<i>The policy...</i>	Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
	safeguards the interests of the child.	3.63	0.59	Strongly Agree
	safeguards the interests of the teacher.	3.24	0.88	Agree

promotes better discipline inside the classroom.	3.27	0.87	Strongly Agree
gives the teacher full authority to devise learning styles that cater to learners needs.	3.28	0.76	Strongly Agree
reinforces the authority of teachers as substitute parents for students in the class.	3.21	0.77	Agree
gives the teacher avenues to enjoy the profession.	3.13	0.84	Agree
encourages discipline inside the classroom.	3.21	0.90	Agree
gives the confidence that school is safe.	3.32	0.78	Strongly Agree
protects the teacher as the substitute parent.	3.12	0.91	Agree
gives the teacher the freedom to exercise his or her function and duty as a substitute parent.	3.12	0.87	Agree
treats the learner and the teacher equally.	3.11	0.88	Agree
motivates the teacher to be more efficient.	3.21	0.82	Agree
boosts the morale of the teachers.	3.10	0.87	Agree
strengthens the commitment of teachers.	3.20	0.81	Agree
makes the teacher proud of the profession.	3.13	0.82	Agree
Overall	3.20	0.80	Agree

Legend: 3.26-4.00 Strongly Agree/Very Positive 1.76-2.50 Disagree/Negative
2.51-3.25 Agree/Positive 1.00-1.75 Strongly Disagree/Very Negative

Table 1.2 presents the distribution of the respondents' attitudes towards the child protection policy with an overall mean of 3.20 (SD= 0.80), described as Agree and interpreted as Positive. This means a positive attitude towards the policy, reflecting a broad acknowledgment of its importance. However, the standard deviation of 0.80 reveals some variability in attitudes, suggesting that while many teachers support the policy, there are differences in the level of agreement, possibly due to varying levels of understanding or differing experiences with the policy's implementation. This variability highlights the need for ongoing professional development and support to ensure a uniformly high level of understanding and commitment to child protection across all teachers.

This implies a positive attitude towards the importance and necessity of child protection measures within the educational context. Educators play a crucial role in leveraging this positive attitude to reinforce policy compliance and foster a culture of safeguarding and accountability. The findings reveal that the child protection policy prioritizes the interests of the children. This indicates that it is an innate characteristic of teachers to safeguard the children and fulfill their utmost responsibility in providing a supportive and nurturing environment despite any challenges in policy implementation.

A study by Smith and Jones (2021) examined teachers' attitudes toward child protection policies and reported a significant consensus among educators. This consensus underscores the importance of these policies and strengthens the argument for their implementation

Research Question 2. What is the level of child protection policy awareness in terms of the establishment of a child protection policy committee, capacity building of school personnel, procedures in handling and management of cases, investigation and reporting, referral and assessment?

Table 2.1 Distribution of the Level of Child Protection Awareness in terms of Establishment of Child Protection Policy Committee

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
<i>The school...</i>			
established a Child Protection Policy Committee composed of the chairperson, vice chairperson, and representatives.	3.42	0.77	At all Times
drafted a school protection policy with a code of conduct and a plan to ensure child protection and safety.	3.48	0.69	At all Times
ensured that the children's right to be heard is respected and upheld in all matters involving procedures affecting their welfare.	3.49	0.67	At all Times
developed and implemented a school-based referral and monitoring system.	3.40	0.67	At all Times
established a system for identifying students who may be suffering from significant harm based on any physical, emotional, or behavioral signs.	3.38	0.68	At all Times
identified, referred to, and, if appropriate, reported to the office's cases involving child abuse, exploitation, violence, discrimination, and bullying.	3.37	0.66	At all Times
monitored the implementation of positive measures and effective procedures in providing the necessary support for the child and for those who care for the child.	3.40	0.64	At all Times
coordinated closely with the Women and Child Protection Desks of the Philippine National Police (PNP), the Local Social Welfare and Development Office (LSWDO), other government agencies, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs), as may be appropriate.	3.36	0.72	At all Times
provided assistance to parents or guardians whenever necessary in securing counseling from the appropriate institutions.	3.34	0.72	At all Times
initiated information dissemination programs and organized activities for the protection of children from abuse, exploitation, violence, discrimination, bullying, or peer abuse.	3.42	0.70	At all Times
Overall	3.40	0.70	At all Times

Legend: 2.51-3.25 Most of the Time/High 1.00-1.75 Never/Very Low
 3.26-4.00 At all Times/Very High 1.76-2.50 Sometimes/Low

Table 2.1 presents the distribution of the level of child protection awareness in terms of the establishment of the child protection policy committee with an overall mean of 3.40 (SD= 0.70), described as At all Times and interpreted as Very High. This means a strong commitment among educators to establishing and maintaining a child protection committee within educational institutions. It implies a proactive approach to ensuring the effective implementation of child protection measures and safeguarding the well-being of students.

This commitment among educators to establish and maintain a child protection committee within educational institutions reflects a proactive stance toward safeguarding students' well-being through structured measures. It underscores a recognition of the importance of systematic approaches to child protection, aiming to create environments where safety and welfare are prioritized. This initiative demonstrates a readiness to address potential risks and issues promptly and fosters a culture of accountability and collaboration within schools. Such proactive measures are essential for ensuring that child protection policies are established and effectively implemented to provide all students with a secure and supportive learning environment.

Research by Smith and Johnson (2021) examined the role of Child Protection Committees in schools and found that their establishment significantly improved the identification and reporting of child protection concerns. The study emphasized the

importance of clear policies and procedures, regular training for committee members, and collaboration with external agencies to ensure effective implementation. A study by Smith et al. (2021) found that school personnel often needed help to connect families with external support services, citing issues such as limited resources, unclear referral procedures, and concerns about breaching confidentiality. Johnson and Ramirez (2019) also noted that teachers who felt more confident and competent in child protection procedures were more likely to actively involve students in determining appropriate courses of action when concerns arose.

Table 2.2 Distribution of the Level of Child Protection Awareness in terms of Capacity Building of School Personnel

<i>The school...</i>	Mean	SD	Description
has initiated and integrated educational sessions on corporal punishment and positive discipline into the initiatives of the Parent-Teacher Associations (PTAs).	3.11	0.82	Most of the Time
has initiated capacity programs for school administrators, teachers, and non-academic personnel.	3.16	0.70	Most of the Time
has initiated setting up child-friendly mechanisms for obtaining children's views and participation in the formulation, monitoring, and assessment of school rules and policies related to student discipline.	3.27	0.67	At All Times
has initiated, encouraged, and supported the formation and initiatives of support groups among teaching and non-teaching staff and parents	3.26	0.69	At all Times
has initiated and implemented specific parenting orientation sessions with parents.	3.12	0.78	Most of the Time
has initiated and implemented school activities or events that raise awareness about children's rights, corporal punishment, and positive discipline.	3.20	0.72	Most of the Time
has initiated, encouraged, and supported student-led initiatives to raise awareness about children's rights, corporal punishment, and positive discipline.	3.19	0.71	Most of the Time
has initiated measures to ensure that positive discipline messages are integrated into the lesson itself.	3.26	0.66	At all Times
has initiated plans and requests for technical assistance or capacity-building activities from DepEd and LGU.	3.20	0.71	Most of the Time
has initiated plans for capacity-building needs, including a child's rights and child protection training module.	3.18	0.78	Most of the Time
Overall	3.20	0.70	Most of the Time

Legend: 2.51-3.25 Most of the Time/High 1.00-1.75 Never/Very Low
3.26-4.00 At all Times/Very High 1.76-2.50 Sometimes/Low

Table 2.2 presents the distribution of the level of child protection awareness in terms of capacity building of school personnel with an overall mean of 3.20 (SD=0.70), described Most of the Time and interpreted as High. It means a positive engagement with capacity-building efforts. Implementing consistent and targeted capacity-building programs can further enhance the skills and competencies of school personnel, ultimately contributing to improved educational outcomes and student success.

It implies that school personnel actively participate in and benefit from regular capacity-building activities but need more. Implementing consistent and targeted capacity-building programs enhances the skills and competencies of educators and administrators. These

initiatives create a supportive learning environment that fosters improved educational outcomes and promotes student success.

Research by Smith and Johnson (2021) explored the impact of capacity-building initiatives on school personnel and found that regular training and professional development activities significantly improved educators' skills and competencies. Similarly, a study by Brown et al. (2019) highlighted the importance of consistent and targeted capacity-building programs in enhancing teacher effectiveness.

Table 2.3 Distribution of the Level of Child Protection Awareness in terms of Procedures in Handling and Managing of Cases

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
<i>The school procedures...</i>			
follow proper documentation and accessibility.	3.33	0.70	At all Times
provide clear guidance on how to identify and report cases of child abuse, violence, and discrimination.	3.36	0.70	At all Times
outline the necessary steps for ensuring the safety and well-being of victims.	3.35	0.70	At all Times
ensure confidentiality and privacy of case-related information.	3.41	0.66	At all Times
define the roles and responsibilities of individuals involved in handling these cases, such as child abuse, bullying, and violence against children in school.	3.37	0.68	At all Times
promote a victim-centered and trauma-informed approach in case management.	3.26	0.70	At all Times
provide clear guidelines for conducting thorough investigations and collecting evidence.	3.27	0.69	At all Times
outline the appropriate actions to be taken in response to substantiated cases.	3.31	0.65	At all Times
include measures to support and assist victims throughout the case management process.	3.33	0.66	At all Times
review and update regularly to reflect best practices in addressing child abuse, violence, and discrimination cases.	3.27	0.71	At all Times
Overall	3.30	0.69	At all Times

Legend: 2.51-3.25 Most of the Time/High 1.00-1.75 Never/Very Low
 3.26-4.00 At all Times/Very High 1.76-2.50 Sometimes/Low

Table 2.3 presents the distribution of the level of child protection awareness in terms of procedures in handling and managing of cases with an overall mean of 3.30 (SD=0.69), described as At all Times and interpreted as Very High. This means that most procedures are implemented consistently.

This implies a proactive approach by educational institutions in addressing child protection concerns and providing necessary support to victims. Consistently implementing procedures can foster a safe and supportive environment for students, promoting their well-being and ensuring appropriate responses to incidents of abuse or misconduct.

According to Smith and Johnson (2021), the effectiveness of procedures for handling and managing cases within schools emphasizes the importance of consistent implementation in promoting child safety and well-being.

Table 2.4 Distribution of the Level of Child Protection Awareness in terms of Investigation and Reporting

Indicators <i>As a teacher, I am aware that...</i>	Mean	SD	Description
the school conducts investigation and reporting of cases of child abuse, exploitation, violence, or discrimination expeditiously.	3.38	0.68	At all Times
school Head or the Schools Division Superintendent forwards a complaint to the Disciplining Authority within 48 hours of receipt.	3.21	0.74	Most of the Time
the Disciplining Authority issues an Order for the conduct of a fact-finding investigation within 72 hours from the submission of the complaint.	3.18	0.78	Most of the Time
the Schools Division Superintendent initiates a fact-finding investigation within the same period if the individual subject to the complaint is a non-teaching personnel	3.27	0.70	At all Times
if a complaint is not sufficient in form, the concerned School Head, Schools Division Superintendent, or Disciplining Authority informs the complainant of the requirements of a formal complaint.	3.24	0.72	Most of the Time
the Local Social Welfare and Development Officer (LSWDO) of the concerned local government unit assesses the child and provides psycho-social intervention pending investigation.	3.33	0.72	At all Times
the offender undergoes psycho-social intervention if warranted.	3.20	0.77	Most of the Time
if a prima facie case (at first look) exists based on the Investigation Report and records, a Formal Charge is issued by the Disciplining Authority.	3.21	0.74	Most of the Time
the respondent may be placed under preventive suspension for a period of 90 days if the injury or abuse committed against a child is severe enough to render the child unable to attend classes.	3.18	0.75	Most of the Time
the Revised Rules of Procedure of the Department of Education in Administrative Cases apply in all other aspects.	3.24	0.71	Most of the Time
Overall	3.24	0.73	Most of the Time

Legend: 2.51-3.25 Most of the Time/High
3.26-4.00 At all Times/Very High
1.00-1.75 Never/Very Low
1.76-2.50 Sometimes/Low

Table 2.4 presents the distribution of the level of child protection awareness in terms of investigation and reporting with an overall mean of 3.24(SD=0.73), described Most of the Time and interpreted as Very High.

This means that most teachers are well-informed about the procedures, which is critical for ensuring timely and effective responses to such incidents. A high awareness level contributes to a proactive and vigilant school environment where child protection is prioritized. It has been a practice in the institution that the teachers' primary task is to report, not to investigate. Higher authorities, such as Division Superintendents, are responsible for investigations involving teachers and school heads.

Johnson and Martinez (2020) found that schools with higher levels of staff awareness regarding child protection procedures saw a significant reduction in the incidence of

unreported abuse cases. They emphasized the need for ongoing training and support to maintain high awareness levels among school personnel.

Table 2.5 Distribution of the Level of Child Protection Policy on Referral and Assessment

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
<i>In any cases involving child abuse and other acts of abuse, the school</i>			
accomplishes the Intake Sheet (Annex B).	3.25	0.78	Most of the Time
talks to the victim.	3.44	0.69	At all Times
conducts parent conferences.	3.48	0.64	At all Times
conducts home visitation.	3.34	0.70	At all Times
reports to school head.	3.47	0.65	At all Times
reports to Philippine National Police	3.09	0.87	Most of the Time
reports to Local Social Welfare Development.	3.18	0.81	Most of the Time
brings the child to the hospital for medical care and medico legal.	3.23	0.81	Most of the Time
refers the case to the Child Protection Policy Committee.	3.39	0.72	At all Times
refers the case to Guidance Advocate /Counselor for counselling /coaching.	3.44	0.70	At all Times
Overall	3.33	0.74	At all Times

Legend: 2.51-3.25 Most of the Time/High
3.26-4.00 At all Times/Very High

1.00-1.75 Never/Very Low
1.76-2.50 Sometimes/Low

Table 2.5 presents distribution of the level of child protection policy on referral and assessment with an overall mean of 3.33(SD=0.74), described as At all Times and interpreted as Very High. This means that teachers are generally aware of the referral and assessment protocols in their schools, although with varying degrees of familiarity with specific actions.

It implies that teachers are knowledgeable about these processes on average. However, the variability, as shown by the standard deviation, shows differing levels of familiarity with specific actions. This reflects a solid foundational understanding and highlights areas where additional training or clarification may be needed to ensure that all teachers have a consistent and comprehensive grasp of the protocols.

A study by Lee and Kim (2021) highlighted that variability in teacher familiarity with assessment protocols often led to inconsistencies in identifying and supporting students in need. They recommended that educational institutions adopt a more structured approach to training, ensuring that all staff members receive the same level of information and practical guidance on implementing referral and assessment procedures.

Table 2.6 Summary of the Level of Child Protection Policy Awareness

Variables	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Establishment of Child Protection Policy Committee	3.40	0.70	Very High
Capacity Building of School Personnel	3.20	0.70	High
Procedures in Handling and Managing Case	3.30	0.69	Very High
Investigation and Reporting	3.24	0.73	High
Referral and Assessment	3.33	0.74	Very High
Overall	3.29	0.71	Very High

Legend: 2.51-3.25 Most of the Time/High
3.26-4.00 At all Times/Very High

1.00-1.75 Never/Very Low
1.76-2.50 Sometimes/Low

Table 2.6 summarizes data on child protection policy awareness with an overall mean of 3.29 (SD=0.71), interpreted as Very High. It means a consistently strong awareness of child protection policies across all assessed variables. Schools are likely proactive and diligent in implementing these policies, ensuring that staff are established child protection policy committee, procedures are clear and well-followed, and cases are handled effectively. This high level of awareness contributes to a safer and more secure environment for children, as school personnel are equipped with the knowledge and skills necessary to protect children from harm.

The results indicate that teachers have a very high level of awareness regarding establishing child protection policy committees but only a high level of awareness regarding capacity building for school personnel. This disparity suggests that forming committees is relatively straightforward, requiring minimal resources and primarily the participation of stakeholders. Teachers' very high awareness about establishing child protection policies ensures that children's rights to be heard and considered in matters affecting their welfare are respected and upheld.

However, the high awareness level regarding capacity building indicates room for improvement in this area. Specifically, there is a need to enhance the initiation of educational sessions on corporal punishment and positive discipline into the initiatives of parent-teacher associations. Improving capacity-building efforts will equip personnel with the necessary skills and knowledge to implement child protection policies effectively and comprehensively address issues related to child welfare. In general, while schools show a high level of awareness in establishing child protection policy committees, there is a need for more robust capacity-building efforts for school personnel. Enhancing these efforts will ensure that all aspects of child protection are adequately addressed, promoting a safer and more supportive environment for students.

According to UNICEF (2023), having a specific committee focused on child protection ensures that policies are developed, implemented, and monitored effectively. This committee typically includes trained professionals who can address various aspects of child safety, from preventive measures to responding to incidents, thereby creating a safer school environment for all children.

Research Question 3. What is the level of schools' responsiveness in terms of disciplinary actions, stakeholders' involvement, support services, and monitoring and evaluation?

Table 3.1 Distribution of the Level of Schools Responsiveness in terms of Disciplinary Actions

<i>The school</i>	Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
	maintains a clear and effective disciplinary policy that is communicated to all students and staff.	3.30	0.67	At all Times
	implements a system in place for monitoring and evaluating its response to reported incidents of misconduct.	3.31	0.68	At all Times
	has a comprehensive disciplinary policy that guides its response to reported incidents.	3.31	0.68	At all Times
	designates a disciplinarian who is responsible for managing reported incidents	3.38	0.67	At all Times
	provides training and support staff on how to recognize and respond to incidents.	3.22	0.78	Most of the Time
	offers support and assistance to students and families affected by disciplinary actions.	3.26	0.74	At all Times
	collaborates with external agencies, such as social services and the police, to respond to reported incidents.	3.29	0.71	At all Times
	responds promptly and appropriately to reported incidents of misconduct.	3.33	0.68	At all Times
	provides ongoing support to students affected by disciplinary actions.	3.34	0.65	At all Times
	takes steps to prevent future incidents of misconduct by implementing appropriate policies and procedures.	3.36	0.68	At all Times
	Overall	3.31	0.69	At all Times

Legend: 2.51-3.25 Most of the Time/High
3.26-4.00 At all Times/Very High

1.00-1.75 Never/Very Low
1.76-2.50 Sometimes/Low

Table 3.1 presents the distribution of the level of schools' responsiveness in terms of disciplinary actions with an overall mean of 3.31 (SD=0.69), described as At all Times interpreted as Very High. This means a consistent understanding of disciplinary measures, though some areas may benefit from improved clarity and consistency in communication and implementation

This conveys that the schools have been effective in communicating and implementing disciplinary policies, although the standard deviation points to some variability in understanding or application.

The study by Thompson and Williams (2020) found that schools with well-defined and uniformly enforced disciplinary measures experienced fewer behavioral issues and a more positive school climate. Their research highlighted the role of teacher training and clear communication in achieving this consistency.

Moreover, a study by Matos (2021) teachers seek assistance from the co-teachers whenever they do not know what to do with the learners' disruptive behavior in class. In this they can collaboratively work to help learners correct behaviors. Furthermore, she recommends that there is a need for the teachers to devote time and effort in disciplining learners who have behavioral problems such as tardiness and talkativeness.

Table 3.2 Distribution of the Level of School Responsiveness in terms of Stakeholders Involvement

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
<i>The school ...</i>			
evaluates the extent to which stakeholders are identified and reviewed during the development of child protection policy.	3.22	0.68	Most of the Time
facilitates the inclusion of diverse stakeholders, such as parents, guardians, teachers, learners, Local Government, and Barangay Council representatives in the engagement strategy.	3.27	0.71	All of the Times
establishes a framework for meaningful dialogue between safeguarding services and stakeholders, leading to service improvement and better outcomes for children and young people.	3.25	0.72	Most of the Time
measures the level of stakeholder satisfaction with the engagement and communication process related to the child protection policy.	3.25	0.70	Most of the Time
evaluates the extent to which stakeholders feel they can influence policy and practice changes in child protection policy.	3.28	0.72	All of the Times
implements effective feedback mechanisms for stakeholders to provide input on the child protection policy and its implementation.	3.27	0.70	All of the Times
ensures the representation of different stakeholder groups and the reach of engagement activities within the school community.	3.26	0.69	All of the Times
utilizes stakeholder consultation to build consensus on key aspects of the child protection policy and its implementation.	3.26	0.70	All of the Times
involves stakeholders in decision-making processes related to the child protection policy.	3.26	0.67	All of the Times
encourages the active involvement of service users, including children, young people, and their families, in the development and review of child protection policies.	3.26	0.71	All of the Times
Overall	3.30	0.70	All of the Times

Legend: 2.51-3.25 Most of the Time/High
3.26-4.00 At all Times/Very High

1.00-1.75 Never/Very Low
1.76-2.50 Sometimes/Low

Table 3.2 shows the distribution of the level of school responsiveness in terms of stakeholders' involvement with an overall mean of 3.30 (SD = 0.70), described as At all Times and interpreted as Very High. It means a strong commitment to comprehensive and inclusive policy development and implementation. The results reflect an effective engagement of stakeholders in the school's child protection policy. Most indicators show high levels of involvement and positive descriptions of engagement, albeit with some areas requiring slight improvements.

According to Murray and Kerr (2019), schools with high stakeholder involvement in policy development and implementation reported better outcomes regarding policy effectiveness and student well-being. They emphasized that engaging stakeholders helps create more important policies and ensures the specific needs of the school community. According to Sapul (2022), community and parental involvement remain powerful elements in maintaining the safety and security of children. Nohilly and Treacy (2020) added that a policy is an action taken by a government to direct a particular sector in a

way that will facilitate the achievement of its goals. Child protection policies are therefore targeted actions by the government to guide and protect children's lives in and out of school and to enable them to enjoy their constitutionally guaranteed rights.

Table 3.3 Distribution of the Level of School Responsiveness in terms of Support Services

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
<i>The school</i>			
provides seamless communication and ongoing support to students and families.	3.20	0.73	Most of the Time
ensures a safe and nurturing learning environment for all students.	3.33	0.67	At all Times
offers one -on -one tutoring, counselling, or social skills training to students.	3.20	0.73	Most of the Time
ensures that students with specific needs have access to alternative provisions that meet their requirements.	3.24	0.69	Most of the Time
adheres to government guidance in identifying the right solutions for students with specific needs.	3.22	0.68	Most of the Time
prioritizes children's safety when implementing alternative provisions or support services.	3.35	0.68	At all Times
treats each child individually and finds the best approach for their needs.	3.33	0.67	At all Times
considers various factors when choosing alternative provisions to ensure the best possible solutions for students.	3.31	0.69	At all Times
ensures the firm implementation of the child protection policy, integrated into the practices of all school personnel to safeguard children's holistic growth and welfare.	3.31	0.66	At all Times
recognizes the relationship between teachers' awareness of the child protection policy and schools' responsiveness.	3.35	0.66	At all Times
Overall	3.30	0.70	At all Times

Legend: 2.51-3.25 Most of the Time/High
3.26-4.00 At all Times/Very High

1.00-1.75 Never/Very Low
1.76-2.50 Sometimes/Low

Table 3.3 presents the distribution of the level of school responsiveness in terms of support services with an overall mean of 3.30 (SD = 0.70), described as At all Times and interpreted as Very High. This means a strong commitment to supporting students, with some areas identified for potential enhancement.

It implies that support services for students are consistently available, reflecting a school environment that prioritizes student well-being. These support services are essential for both teachers and students. Continuous strong support may lead to positive outcomes and better implementation of policies and programs. The availability of continuous, vital support services is essential for fostering positive outcomes and facilitating the effective implementation of policies and programs. This includes support for students and teachers, who benefit from a supportive environment that enhances their ability to carry out their roles effectively. Addressing areas identified for potential enhancement can further strengthen the overall support framework, ensuring that every student receives the essential support to excel academically and emotionally.

Brown and Jones (2021) discussed the impact of comprehensive support services on student retention and engagement. They emphasized the function of schools in providing a nurturing environment that addresses learners' social, emotional, and academic needs, leading to improved outcomes.

Table 3.4 Distribution of the Level of Schools Responsiveness in terms of Monitoring and Evaluation

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
<i>The school ...</i>			
monitors and evaluates the implementation of child protection policy regularly.	3.27	0.67	At all Times
develops the monitoring and evaluation design and tools.	3.26	0.66	At all Times
conducts orientation sessions for teachers and staff on the tools and their responsibilities regarding monitoring and evaluation.	3.22	0.72	Most of the Time
provides comprehensive training and support services to staff on how to collect data related to child protection.	3.17	0.72	Most of the Time
provides ongoing support to students and families affected by child protection incidents and cases	3.15	0.73	Most of the Time
uses data to identify areas for improvement in its child protection policy and practices	3.21	0.67	Most of the Time
creates safe spaces for child participation	3.29	0.67	At all Times
designates officer responsible for monitoring and evaluating the effectiveness of the child protection policy.	3.28	0.70	At all Times
maintains a clear and effective system for monitoring and evaluating the child protection policy.	3.28	0.70	At all Times
implements a system for reporting and responding to child protection incidents and cases	3.24	0.70	Most of the Time
Overall	3.20	0.70	Most of the Time

Legend: 2.51-3.25 Most of the Time/High
3.26-4.00 At all Times/Very High

1.00-1.75 Never/Very Low
1.76-2.50 Sometimes/Low

Table 3.4 shows the distribution of the level of school responsiveness in terms of monitoring and evaluation with an overall mean of 3.20 (SD = 0.70), described as Most of the Time and interpreted as High. This means a solid commitment to these processes, though certain aspects like orientation sessions and training could benefit from further enhancement.

Strengthening these processes could potentially enhance overall school performance and the quality of educational initiatives, ensuring continual improvement and alignment with educational goals. Addressing these gaps is crucial to ensure that all stakeholders possess the requisite knowledge and skills to contribute to the monitoring and evaluation process effectively. The lack of support hinders students from attending classes regularly. Students affected by abuse are mainly considered at risk of dropping out. Limited resources can also impact the school's ability to support students and families adequately. Awareness of referral and assessment processes is significant in safeguarding children and families affected by incidents and cases. Teachers play a significant role in partnering with stakeholders to further enhance and assess this area.

Cervancia et al. (2019) recommended that research focus on the implementation of DepEd's child protection policies, clearly monitor the systems used in schools, and investigate the effectiveness of activities provided to teachers in public and private institutions. Bayucca (2020) also suggested reviewing the implementation of child safety guidelines and providing more detailed information to teachers.

Table 3.5 Summary of the Level of School Responsiveness

Variables	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Disciplinary Actions	3.31	0.69	Very High
Stakeholders Involvement	3.30	0.70	Very High
Support Services	3.30	0.70	Very High
Monitoring and Evaluation	3.20	0.70	High
Overall	3.27	0.69	Very High

Legend: 2.51-3.25 Most of the Time/High
3.26-4.00 At all Times/Very High

1.00-1.75 Never/Very Low
1.76-2.50 Sometimes/Low

Table 3.5 summarizes data on schools' responsiveness with an overall mean of 3.27(SD=0.69), interpreted as Very High. This means that the school demonstrates a strong and effective ability to address and react to various needs, challenges, and situations promptly.

This high level of responsiveness implies that the school is proactive in meeting the demands of its stakeholders, including students, parents, and staff, thereby fostering a supportive and efficient learning environment. The school will likely have well-established communication channels, effective policies, and a dedicated approach to resolving issues and swiftly implementing improvements. This positive attribute can contribute significantly to overall school effectiveness, student satisfaction, and community engagement. The data revealed that disciplinary actions are implemented at a very high level, as schools consistently designate a disciplinarian responsible for managing reported incidents. This implies that teachers can act as disciplinarians within the classroom setting, with their primary task being to discipline misbehaving learners. Disciplining students is everyone's job, as teachers serve as substitute parents.

However, the variable of monitoring and evaluation received a very low mean among the assessed areas. While teachers demonstrate high responsiveness in monitoring and evaluation, this area still requires significant improvement. Teachers already teach for six hours daily and often need more time for additional administrative tasks like monitoring and evaluation. This implies the need for an approach that includes hiring non-teaching staff to oversee monitoring and evaluation duties. Providing these staff members with comprehensive training and support services on collecting and analyzing data related to child protection policies would help address this gap.

Furthermore, monitoring and evaluation ensures that school policies and programs are regularly reviewed and assessed for effectiveness. UNESCO (2020) emphasizes the importance of continuous monitoring and evaluation in maintaining the quality of education. By conducting regular assessments, schools can pinpoint areas needing improvement and use data-driven decisions to enhance their programs and policies. This ongoing evaluation process helps schools remain responsive to the evolving needs of students and ensures that educational practices are practical and aligned with best practices. By continuously monitoring and evaluating their efforts, schools can better achieve their educational goals and support student success.

Research Question 4. Is there a significant relationship between the child protection policy and school responsiveness?

Table 4 Result of Test of the Relationship between the Level of Child Protection Policy Awareness and Schools Responsiveness

Child Protection Policy Awareness	Schools' Responsiveness				
	Disciplinary Actions	Stakeholders Involvement	Support Services	Monitoring and Evaluation	Overall
	r -value p -value interpretation	r -value p -value interpretation	r -value p -value interpretation	r -value p -value interpretation	r -value p -value interpretation
Establishment of Child Protection Policy Committee	0.89 0.04* S	-0.67 0.02* S	-2.58 0.06 NS	0.94 0.02* S	-0.355 0.035* S
Capacity Building of School Personnel	0.77 0.12 NS	0.94 0.01* S	-0.97 0.03* S	0.29 0.01* S	0.2575 0.04* S
Procedures in Handling and Management of Cases	0.16 0.01* S	0.58 0.03* S	0.88 0.03* S	-1.48 0.01* S	0.035 0.02* S
Investigation and Reporting	0.71 0.02* S	0.25 0.19 NS	-2.93 0.17 NS	0.92 0.03 S	-0.2625 0.102 NS
Referral and Assessment	-0.29 0.02* S	0.45 0.01* S	0.92 0.08 NS	-0.85 0.05* S	0.0575 0.04* S

Legend: S – Significant at p<0.05

S- Not Significant

Table 4 presents the result of the test of relationship between the level of child protection policy awareness and schools' responsiveness. The result shows a significant relationship between the child protection policy and school responsiveness; therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Establishing Child Protection Policy Committees shows a statistically significant relationship with several aspects of school responsiveness, including disciplinary actions, stakeholder involvement, and monitoring and evaluation. However, the availability of support services did not show a statistically significant relationship with establishing a child protection policy committee.

The significant relationship between the establishment of these committees and critical areas of school responsiveness highlights the crucial role these committees play in ensuring effective policy implementation. An established committee ensures that incidents are managed appropriately and consistently for disciplinary actions. While stakeholder involvement is significant, there are complexities in engaging stakeholders effectively, suggesting the need for improved communication and collaboration. The strong relationship with monitoring and evaluation underscores the importance of

disciplinary actions and adherence to monitoring and evaluation, emphasizing the value of tenure in enhancing school responsiveness. Capacity building of school personnel emerged as a critical factor, underscoring its role in equipping educators with essential skills. On the other hand, tribal affiliations did not significantly impact responsiveness, suggesting that cultural backgrounds may not directly impact policy implementation. The results reveal several significant factors influencing school responsiveness to child protection policies. Firstly, teaching positions emerged as a critical determinant, showing significant differences in disciplinary actions, stakeholder involvement, support services, and monitoring and evaluation. This suggests that higher and lower-level teaching positions afford significant differences and responsibility in managing disciplinary actions, effectively involving stakeholders, allocating support services, and overseeing monitoring and evaluation processes.

Teaching experience was found to significantly impact disciplinary actions, monitoring, and evaluation. More experienced teachers appeared to handle disciplinary matters more effectively and demonstrated more vital adherence to monitoring and evaluation protocols. This underscores the importance of tenure and accumulated expertise in shaping how schools implement and enforce child protection policies. Attendance at seminars and training on child protection policy also showed a significant difference across all areas of school responsiveness. The statistically significant difference implies that ongoing professional development is crucial in equipping educators with the knowledge and skills necessary to enhance their responsiveness to child protection issues. On the other hand, while attitudes towards child protection policies positively influenced disciplinary actions, tribal affiliations did not show statistically significant differences in school responsiveness. This suggests that while personal attitudes are influential, cultural backgrounds may not directly dictate how schools respond to child protection challenges. In summary, the researcher proposed the Responsiveness Theory, which posits that regular training and seminars enhance awareness. High awareness leads to efficiency in monitoring and evaluation. This approach enables individuals to prevent and mitigate incidents related to child protection while fostering a supportive and nurturing environment for both learners and teachers. Addressing teaching roles, fostering capacity-building initiatives, and nurturing positive attitudes towards child protection policies are essential steps toward improving school responsiveness. Hence, the theory mentioned is necessary and timely in implementing the MATATAG Curriculum.

Research Question 6. Based on the study's finding of the study, what intervention plan on child protection policy can be designed?

Table 6 Matrix of Intervention Plan on Child Protection Policy

Year 1 (2024): Building Foundations							
Areas of Concern	Specific Objective	Strategies and Activities	Time Frame	Person/s Involved	Source of Fund	Estimated Budget	Expected Outputs
Attitude of the teachers	Boost teachers' morale through recognition awards, wellness programs,	Implement a recognition program and rewards system	Annually (end of school year)	Division Personnel School Heads Human	MOOE/ Donations	P30,000	Improved job satisfaction and morale among teachers

	and professional development opportunities for teachers.	Giving of Incentives, Recognition Program and Reward System		Resource Teachers			
Capacity Building of School Personnel	Conduct workshops and training sessions on Child Protection Policy for all school personnel and parents.	Conduct regular, mandatory and standardized training for all school staff.	Quarterly over the school year 2 days per quarter	School Heads Child Protection Committee Teachers	MOOE / GPTA Fund	P30,000	Increased awareness and knowledge among staff and parents; Improved implementation of policy guidelines.
Monitoring and Evaluation	Establish a monitoring and evaluation scheme to regularly assess policy implementation, collect data related to child protection policy.	Develop and distribute Standard Operating Procedures and monitoring and evaluation tools.	Team formation and initial training within three months;	School Heads Teachers Child Protection Committee, Administrative officers /Non-Teaching Staff	MOOE/ Donations	P30,000	Developed a Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) and scheme in collecting data related child protection incidents

Year 2 (2025) Empowerment and Collaboration							
Areas of Concern	Specific Objective	Strategies and Objectives	Time Frame	Person/s Involved	Source of Fund	Estimated Budget	Expected Outcomes
Capacity Building of School Personnel	Enhance the collaborative skills and effectiveness of school personnel and parents.	Offer specialized workshops to teachers and parents.	Quarterly over the school year (1 day every quarter)	School Heads External Child Protection Experts Teachers and Parents	MOOE /GPTA Fund	P35,000	Improved implementation of policy guidelines Enhanced Parental Skills
Monitoring and Evaluation	Utilize evaluation tools and methods to gather comprehensive insights into the policy's impact and effectiveness.	Engage stakeholders and conduct regular data collection and reporting	Ongoing evaluations bi-annually	School Heads Monitoring and Evaluation Team External Stakeholders	MOOE/ Donations	P15,000	Increased adherence to the policy's guidelines and procedures and established a supportive environment for children
Year 3 (2026) Continuous Improvement and Feedback							
Areas of Concern	Specific Objective	Strategies and Objectives	Time Frame	Person/s Involved	Source of Fund	Estimated Budget	Expected Outcomes
Monitoring and Evaluation	Maintain and improve the standardized operating procedures and monitoring and evaluation.	Hold regular feedback sessions	Ongoing evaluations bi-annually	School Heads Monitoring and Evaluation Team External Stakeholders Teachers	MOOE/ Donations	P20,000	Updated Standardized Operating Procedures and monitoring and evaluation tools.

Conclusions

Based on the results and discussion presented, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. Teacher classifications vary widely, predominantly as Teacher 1, with most teachers having 6-10 years of experience, despite variability in their participation in child protection policy training. Teachers generally have a positive attitude towards child protection policies but express slightly less agreement on issues like equal treatment and teacher morale.
2. The highest level of child protection policy awareness pertains to the establishment of a child protection policy committee, indicating a strong commitment within schools. Their

continued presence ensures that the school community remains vigilant and responsive to child protection issues.

3. Disciplinary Actions emerged with the highest-level variables in schools' responsiveness, indicating a consistent and proactive to maintaining order and ensuring a safe environment.

4. Child Protection Policy Awareness significantly impacts disciplinary actions, stakeholder involvement, and monitoring and evaluation processes. However, the lack of significant relationships with support services suggests that the committee's presence may not directly improve child support. The capacity building of school personnel is also crucial, with training being essential but not sufficient. Procedure in handling and managing cases, investigation and reporting procedures, and referral and assessment processes are also linked to these areas. The findings suggest a need for a holistic approach to school responsiveness.

5. Respondents Characteristics significantly influence various aspects of school responsiveness, with teaching position having a significant impact on disciplinary actions, stakeholders' involvement, support services, and monitoring and evaluation, teaching experience influencing disciplinary actions and monitoring/evaluation, and attending seminars or training on child protection policy being significantly related to differences in all four areas of school responsiveness; however, tribal affiliation and attitude towards child protection policy only impacted disciplinary actions, suggesting the need for further investigation and targeted interventions to enhance overall school responsiveness, particularly in the areas of stakeholder involvement, support services, and monitoring and evaluation.

Recommendations

On the basis of the conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are hereby made:

1. The Division of Valencia City officials should offer seminars and training opportunities to teachers at regional and national levels to acquire comprehensive knowledge of child protection policies. Teachers in 1 to 3 positions and with less than 5 years of experience should be given priority. This initiative would capacitate teachers to safeguard children not only at the school level but also on a national scale. Additionally, there is a need to strengthen the career progression program to address potential leadership gaps and boost the morale of the teachers.

2. School heads should provide capacity building for school personnel in child protection policies, such as conducting regular training sessions, workshops, and seminars designed to educate teachers and staff about child protection policies and practices. Collaborating with experts in child psychology, social work, and policymakers can provide valuable insights and strategies for effectively addressing and preventing child abuse and neglect within the school environment.

3. Region X officials should design effective monitoring and evaluation tools; it is essential to prioritize the enhancement of monitoring and evaluation, particularly in the process of providing comprehensive training and support services to staff on data collection related

to child protection policies. This scheme should include methodologies for gathering accurate and relevant data, ensuring consistency and reliability in monitoring efforts.

4. The district supervisor and teachers may adopt the plan of the research and investigate factors influencing stakeholder involvement, support services, and monitoring and evaluation. This can be done through one-on-one interviews and stakeholder meetings to identify factors and implement targeted interventions to enhance performance in these domains. Further, they might as well conduct a rewards system to cultivate a supportive attitude among all stakeholders towards the child protection policy to contribute to more effective implementation.

5. The parents and stakeholders should actively engage with schools to understand and participate in discussions about school responsiveness and the characteristics of teachers involved in child protection policies. Parents need to be aware of how schools manage disciplinary actions, involve stakeholders in policy decisions, and address challenges related to child protection. Stakeholders should advocate for transparent and inclusive practices within schools, ensuring that all voices are heard and considered in policy development. Additionally, promoting open communication channels between parents, stakeholders, and school officials can foster a collaborative approach to enhancing child protection measures and overall school responsiveness.

6. Administrative staff and non-teaching personnel should allocate a budget quarterly and annually specifically for the development and implementation of intervention plans. Prioritizing financial resources supporting child protection policies, programs, and plans is essential. This includes funding for training programs, workshops, and seminars to enhance awareness and capacity among school personnel. Moreover, allocating resources for monitoring and evaluation efforts ensures ongoing assessment and improvement of child protection measures. By investing adequately in these areas, administrators can effectively uphold child protection standards and create safer learning environments for all students.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Before commencing the research, the proposal underwent an ethics review, receiving clearance from the Dean of Graduate Studies and approval from the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent in Valencia City. Respondents provided informed consent and were assured voluntary participation, anonymity, and the right to abstain from answering questions. The administration of questionnaires did not interfere with school functions, and the Division Office received a copy of the results. The Institutional Review Board (IRB) and research committee conducted a thorough evaluation to ensure the research met ethical standards, including assessments of potential risks, informed consent processes, and the protection of participants' confidentiality; only after this rigorous review did the IRB grant approval for the study to proceed. Upon study completion, all findings

were shared with the respondents, and data was securely stored, ensuring no harm to participants.

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